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Article Title:**Tolerance for Adoption of Ethically Controversial Practices: A Survey of
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Abstract

Considering journalistic ethics as being constructed and negotiated by journalists in an everyday work routine, this study seeks to measure journalists' ethical orientation through respondents' tolerance toward twelve common ethically controversial practices (ECPs) in the journalism field. A cross-sectional survey through administering a close-ended questionnaire was carried out on a purposive sample of 250 journalists in Sindh province, Pakistan to investigate their opinions on various ECPs. Regarding demographic characteristics, the findings show that the majority of the surveyed respondents are male, aged between 31-40 years, having the highest education bachelor level degree, and working for Sindhi language print media organizations with professional experience of up to 10 years. Further, it was found that the majority of the journalists show displeasure over the adoption of ten ethically controversial practices. However, two practices tend to be acceptable in certain situations. Added the journalists associated with print media tend to be more tolerant toward ECPs as compared to those who were associated with electronic media. However, the findings in terms of the language of the media organizations and the journalistic experience of the respondent journalists are mixed and not consensual.

Keywords: *Ethics, Controversial Practices, Journalists, Perceived Tolerance.*

Introduction

Ethics is derived from the Greek word *ethos*, which refers to "custom," "usage," or "character." Scholars, as well as philosophers, think of it as a sane progression applying well-established principles in case of collision between two moral obligations. The ethical situation becomes the most critical when there is a conflict between two right obligations. In this way, ethics regularly revolve around balancing competing values in the absence of any correct answer to ethical dilemmas(Thakurta, 2009).

The notions regarding the rightness or wrongness of action of society are reflected by ethics. Many dilemmas in everyday life cannot be answered simply as right or wrong. Those dilemmas are resolved by ethics whose theories date back centuries. Application of those theories helps human beings in answering such tricky questions in the time of confusion and dilemmas(Patterson, Wilkins, & Painter, 2018).

Ethics and Journalists

Debate on the ethical attitudes of journalists seems very tedious. These days journalists, advertisers, and public relations personnel have become subject

to severe criticism. Journalists often perform their professional duties of reporting under severe constraints such as economic pressures and organizational pressures. Under such pressures, a journalist is bound to double-check balance and objectivity in the news before filing it. Such ethical actions always put a journalist under a dilemma that can be resolved by applying ethical theory (Christians, Fackler, Richardson, & Kreshel, 2020).

Media workers often defend their action of intrusion into others' private lives based on "the people's right to know". The major issue with such an answer is that it fails to answer a query regarding "what the people have a right to know" and "why the public has a right to this kind of information in the first place" (Ward, 2013, 2015).

Thus, the ethical orientation of news workers is essential because it mirrors and forms functional and professional parameter; administer news work practices and show the formal state of journalistic professionalism. Since, on a micro-level, ethical consideration is a personal activity, a considerable body of research on media ethics concentrates on applying both individual and societal levels (Plaisance, 2013).

Based on the argument that news workers construct, reconstruct and negotiate journalistic ethics over time, the researchers have examined and evaluated ethical orientations of journalists by measuring their attitudes to ethically controversial practices by employing survey methods. In their daily work routines, journalists often confront manifold pressures and restrictions in producing news. News workers often find themselves in a dilemma whether to resort to any ethically questionable practices. These practices may include pressurizing sources, paying them for information, use of confidential data, adoption of anyone else's identity, manipulation of photos, and others (Day, 2005; Plaisance, Skewes, & Hanitzsch, 2012).

Lee, Cui, and Zhang (2015) deny accepting any linear and direct association between accepting a controversial practice and being unethical. In real-life situations, several moral standards and professional values perhaps come in confrontation with each other in tangible circumstances and journalists may assume various otherwise unethical practices acceptable in some situations. For example, using clandestine cameras and adopting other's identities may sometimes become essential for investigating an important news story when it is not possible to gather information through usual means of reporting. Most vital to this study is the fact that journalists' less tolerance toward ECPs might be reinforced by their leaning toward relativistic orientation (Fröhlich, Koch, & Obermaier, 2013).

Lee et al. (2015) aptly define the normative relationship of journalists with journalistic ethics as "Construction and reconstruction of journalistic ethics unfolds as a process bearing a direct relation to how journalists do their work. Journalists constantly engage in moral reasoning in their daily work. They are, therefore, at the forefront of the reconstruction of professional ethics" (pp. 205).

Pakistan, particularly Sindh province, is an ideal site for tackling the issue of media ethics in general and journalists' understanding, views, attitudes, perception of media ethics in particular. The country affords a new news atmosphere with exponential reconfigurations. In the last two decades, the media enterprise has endured a wide range of reforms such as liberalization or privatization, the establishment of regulatory bodies. It would be wise to say that it has moved away from the state-owned model, yet the state owns its old media organizations such as Pakistan Broadcasting Corporation, Pakistan Television, and Associated Press of Pakistan.

Liberalization of electronic media during the period of President of Pakistan General Pervez Musharaf offered an exponential rise to the number of TV channels in the country. Previously, only state-owned TV channels were the major source of information, entertainment, and opinion formation for the public. Now, the number of private TV channels has exceeded fifty, and more are pouring in. The growing number of media outlets demanded more workforces throughout the country. Hence, media owners started employing inexperienced, untrained, and unprofessional individuals as reporters which, in turn, resulted in creating more ethical dilemmas in the industry.

Thus, the new media environment coupled with competition and commercialization, technological innovation, changing role conception of journalists, commercial and political influences caused many ethical issues in journalism. In this way, this study does not aim at critiquing journalism ethics in Pakistan from a normative perspective though. Rather, the empirical analysis is expected to shed light on how various factors influence journalists' ethical judgment, which should give us insights into how journalism ethics may continue to evolve.

Literature Review

Ethical judgment, almost all the time, is found based on contemplation of differing values which originate from inner motivations and outer pressures. It is considered bedrock for ethical decision-making in many academic as well as commercial disciplines including journalism (Voakes, 1997). Both journalists' and their organizations' credibility and professionalism are based on and can be greatly affected by such ethical judgments. The importance of journalism ethics for readers and viewers cannot be undermined at all. For citizens, simultaneously, are consumers as well as sources of a news story, and their lives are greatly affected by the decisions of journalists (Hanitzsch, 2007).

Journalists in South Asia in general, and in Pakistan, particular, perform their duties under increasingly tough and difficult atmosphere. They face multifaceted pressures to uncover corruption and political and corporate offenses (Mezzera & Sial, 2010), which could, on a basic level, underscore the utilitarian or consequence-oriented approach to ethical decision-making.

The concept of universal ethical norms in the field of journalism is not a novel one. 'Journalist's Creed,' a document which features few standards of ethical guidelines in the profession, was made in 1941. Later on, it was translated into more than 100 languages and distributed in numerous countries. Many International Codes of Ethics for journalists were also inspired by this document (Ferreira, 2014: 18-19). However, the adoption of this code of ethics was affected greatly by regional politico-social events throughout the world such as Cold War, etc. Regional events, indigenous culture, political issues, and journalistic standards are likely to impact ethical points of view adopted by journalists.

In this regard, (Hallin & Mancini, 2004), in their seminal and most widely cited work, have studied that societal structures affect journalistic styles. Weaver and Willnat (2012) have focused on journalists' professional roles, norms, and cultures. Additionally, in an ongoing promising project titled "Worlds of Journalism Study", Hanitzsch et al. (2011) have strived to investigate journalism culture around the globe. Comparative studies in journalism have indicated that despite global convergence, local and regional factors still play a vital part in influencing differences in orientations (Hanitzsch et al., 2011).

Recently, Hanitzsch et al. (2011) have conducted a comparative study on journalism ethics. Under their developed framework, they conceptualize ethical ideologies as an integral part of journalism culture. Their findings suggest that a majority of journalists comply with universal principles of ethics. Most journalists strive to stay away from questionable methods of reporting, however, findings in terms of resorting to ethically controversial practices in reporting varied across nations (see Hanitzsch et al., 2011: 285). Comparative research on ethical orientation has discovered a high degree of correspondence among Brazilian, American, Australian, Swiss, and German reporters in their tendency to support universal ethical principles and their dismissal of adoption of controversial practices. Journalism scholars have additionally discovered that news workers in "developing and transitional contexts" often tend to be more concerned about the feedback of their reports rather than the method through which they get the story (Hanitzsch et al., 2011: 284).

Most important is to note that Hanitzsch et al.'s (2011) research was primarily based upon seeking reporters' opinion on the adoption of ethically controversial practices without focusing on a particular methodology. Secondly, ethical orientation, inter alia, was only one part of their developed framework on journalism culture. This examination expands on past work by concentrating on journalists in Sindh, Pakistan, and their views on ethically controversial practices.

Mellado, Moreira, Lagos, and Hernández (2012), conducted an interesting study on journalism cultures in Latin America. They analyzed, among other variables, the ethical ideologies of journalists in three Latin American nations. In this comparative study, researchers found that most journalists follow and strive for universal ethical principles. The study also found Chilean journalists more flexible towards the adoption of ethically controversial practices in reporting to get a story. The authors point out, with variations, that among other reasons the

rise of investigative journalism may potentially be a major reason behind the prevalence of this trend (Mellado, 2012). As these researchers bring up, it is conceivable that ethical orientations may shift even inside newsrooms.

In their seminal study on American journalists' role and ethics, Weaver et al. (2009), found the newsroom setting as the most dominant factor impacting US journalists' ethical decision-making; although family and religion still assumed a powerful influence. One may conclude that journalists might acquire and receive ethical viewpoints when they connect the profession with an academic setting. However, this paper limits the centralization of an investigation by concentrating on ethically controversial practices.

Objectives and Hypotheses of Study

1. To assess the acceptance level for 'use of unauthorized information' by journalists in Sindh
2. To assess the acceptance level for 'journalistic deception' by journalists in Sindh
3. To assess the acceptance level for 'information manipulation' by journalists in Sindh

Hypotheses

1. Journalists in Sindh do not support to 'use of unauthorized information'
2. Journalists in Sindh do not support to 'journalistic deception'
3. Journalists in Sindh do not support to 'information manipulation'

Research Design

The purpose of this study was to measure the tolerance level of journalists in Sindh province, Pakistan for adopting ethical controversial practices. For that purpose, quantitative research was conducted. Quantitative research is defined as "a systematic investigation of phenomena by gathering quantifiable data and performing statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques" (Wimmer & Dominick, 2013, p. 213). The methodology was chosen because, in the absence of any other descriptive and explanatory study, it is better to opt for quantifiable data. In the first place, it helps the researcher in exploring a prevailing situation, satisfies a researcher's curiosity for better understanding, helps in testing the feasibility of taking out a more extensive study (Babbie, 2013, p. 94).

Following existing literature in the domain and keeping in mind the research objective, the researcher carried out a cross-sectional survey to investigate the research question. As survey method has widely and successfully been used in media research for a long. According to Wimmer and Dominick

(2014:192), surveys have a variety of advantages in media research. Gunter (2000) also emphasizes on survey by terming them a suitable strategy to quantify and measure phenomena numerically.

Population and Sampling

The population of this study was journalists in Sindh province, Pakistan. However, very rarely the whole population is studied because the process is cost-prohibitive and challenges measurement scales. Additionally, no complete inventory of the journalists working in Sindh, Pakistan was available. Since, keeping in mind vast area of study, the research covered Hyderabad division in Sindh province, Pakistan as sampled purposively. The division is administratively divided into nine districts including Hyderabad city, Jamshoro, Dadu, Thatta, Sujawal, Badin, Tando Muhammad Khan, Tando Allahyar, and Matiari.

The study focused on those journalists only who were working as a media person in district headquarters. Though journalists work and can be found in every sub-district of the Hyderabad division, the main reason behind choosing district headquarters are; firstly, government apparatus like Police and District governments, work actively in district headquarters. Therefore, these cities are more developed as compared to other sub-districts. Secondly, in the wake of allocated time and finance for this study, it was not possible to include journalists from all over Sindh.

Data Collection

A questionnaire was adapted encompassing the construct regarding ethically controversial practices. The questionnaire was administered among the subjects of the study by the researcher himself in person. Hence, such interaction ensured that respondents were guided in case of any confusion. The researcher visited all nine districts himself. Moreover, for the sake of clarity and validity, the questionnaire was also translated into Sindhi and Urdu languages. For Sindhi, a proficient bilingual person was hired. The same process was adopted for getting the questionnaire translated into Urdu. Then other two proficient persons in both the languages were hired for back translating the questionnaires into English. That translation was also reviewed by a bilingual professor with extensive experience in languages. The reliability of the questionnaire and the field procedure were tested by conducting a pilot study among the sub-sample of the population of the journalists.

Operational definition of the construct

Ethically Controversial Practices (ECPs): Ethically controversial practices mainly refer to concrete practices in everyday journalistic professional work (Day, 2006). Based on Lee's (2005), Day's (2006), and Lee et al.'s (2015) discussion, this construct measured tolerance for Ethically Controversial Practices by asking respondents

whether they see 12 practices as acceptable. The answering categories included 1=unacceptable in any situations, 2= acceptable in certain situations, and 3=acceptable in most situations.

Results And Findings

Demographic and Professional Profile of the Journalists

Demographic Profile

Table 1: *Composition of the journalists by demographic variables*

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	248	(99.2)
Female	2	(0.8)
Age category		
Up to 30 years	76	(30.4)
31 to 40 years	97	(38.8)
Above 40 years	77	(30.8)
Education		
Intermediate and less	64	(25.6)
Bachelor	111	(44.4)
Masters	75	(30.0)

See table 1 first in the context of gender almost all the journalists were male. Second, the majority (69.6%) of the respondents were up to 40 years old. Regarding education, the highest proportion of the journalists had bachelor's degrees. Conclusively, it mentioned that the typical journalist was male and belonged to the age category ranging from thirty-one to forty-year-old. In the context of education, the typical journalist had a maximum bachelor-level degree.

Professional profile

Table1: *Composition of the journalists by profession related variables*

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Organization Type		
Electronic Media	50	(20.0)
Print Media	133	(53.2)
Multiple Media	67	(26.8)
Organization Language		
Sindhi	153	(61.2)
Urdu	58	(23.2)
English	12	(4.8)
Multiple	27	(10.8)
Journalistic experience		

Up to 10 years	122	(48.8)
11 to 20 years	76	(30.4)
Above 20	52	(20.8)
<i>Monthly Income</i>		
Nil/Voluntary	111	(44.4)
Up to 20000/= PKR	104	(41.6)
Above 20000/=PKR	35	(14.0)

See table 2 first in terms of media organization type, it surfaced that the simple majority of the surveyed journalists worked for print media organizations. Second, regarding the language of the media organizations, the majority of the journalists worked for Sindhi language media organizations. Third, in connection with journalistic experience, the highest proportion accounting for almost fifty percent of the surveyed journalists had journalistic experience up to 10 years. Lastly, regarding monthly income, the majority of the surveyed journalists expressed that they worked voluntarily or un-paid. Conclusively, it was summarized that the typical surveyed journalist is trademarked as a print journalist and worked for a Sindhi language media organization. Moreover, he had journalistic experience maximum of up to ten years and worked as a volunteer or up-paid.

Tolerance for Ethically Controversial Practices (ECPs)

Table 3: *Journalists' Tolerance for ECPs (%)*

Tolerance for ECPs	1	2	3	Mean(SD)
Category 01, Use of unauthorized information				
Offering monetary incentives to sources for confidential information	52.8	42.4	4.8	1.52(.59)
Unauthorized use of confidential commercial or government documents	50.0	38.4	11.6	1.62(.69)
Claiming oneself to be someone else (false identification)	60.0	35.6	4.4	1.44(.58)
Pressuring sources to get news	60.4	33.6	6.0	1.46(.61)
Category 02, Journalistic deception				
Unauthorized use of personal documents such as letters and photos	54.8	39.6	5.6	1.51(.60)
Getting employed in a firm to get inside information	50.4	44.8	4.8	1.54(.59)
Use of hidden cameras or microphones	18.0	65.6	16.4	1.98(.59)
Recreating a news event	41.6	49.2	9.2	1.68(.64)
Category 03, Information manipulation				
Publishing or airing unverified information	87.2	10.0	2.8	1.16(.43)
Receiving money from sources	88.4	7.2	4.4	1.16(.47)
Altering or manufacturing quotes	66.4	30.8	2.8	1.36(.54)
Altering photos	76.4	19.2	4.4	1.28(.54)

(N = 250) Scale ranges from 1 = unacceptable in any situation; 2 = acceptable in certain situations; 3 = acceptable in most situations.

Using principal component analysis with oblique rotation technique, an exploratory factor analysis test was run to find if latent dimensions are underlying the 12 items. As a result, three factors with Eigenvalues greater than 1 emerged. Items 9, 5, 12, 10, 11, and 4 listed belonged to a factor one; items 2, 3, and 6 belonged to a factor two; items 7,8, and 1 belonged to factor three. However, the total variance of the three factors with Eigenvalue > 1 was 49.23; which is less than the acceptable variance ratio for exploratory factor analysis. Therefore, the 12 items are used separately, considering them as belonging to three conceptual categories, as did Lee, Cui & Zhang (2015), when discussing the descriptive statistics.

Table 3 presents data regarding the journalists' attitude toward ECPs. About the first conceptual category "Use of unauthorized information" four statements were asked to measure the attitude of the journalists regarding the perceived acceptability of the ECPs. While observing the items, it was found that the majority of the journalists said for all the four items that are "offering monetary incentives to sources for confidential information", "Unauthorized use of confidential commercial or government documents", "Claiming oneself to be someone else (false identification)", and "pressuring sources to get news" are unacceptable in any situation. Whereas, under the second conceptual category "journalistic deception" out of four the first two items that are "Unauthorized use of personal documents such as letters and photos" and "Getting employed in a firm to get inside information" are "unacceptable in any situation" for the majority of the surveyed journalists. However, about the remaining two items that is "use of hidden cameras or microphones" and "recreating a news event" the journalists showed a positive sign that those activities are "acceptable in certain situations." Finally, regarding the third conceptual category "Information manipulation" about all four items that are "publishing or airing unverified information", "receiving money from sources", "altering or manufacturing quotes", and "altering photos" the great majority of the journalists said that they are "unacceptable in any situation".

Overall, while looking at the findings, we came to know that the results are similar to the study of (Mellado et al., 2012). As she and her colleagues also found Mexican, Brazilian and Chilean journalists opposing acceptance of ECPs. In the same way, the results of this study are also similar to the study of (Joyce, Saldaña, Weiss, & Alves, 2017). As they also found that almost 70% of surveyed respondents considered the item 'use of hidden cameras or microphones' justifiable in some cases. On the other hand, few findings are in contrast with (Lee et al., 2015) study. As they found nearly half of the respondents considering two practices - offering monetary incentives to sources to get news and adoption of false identification - acceptable in most situations. Whereas, those items got lower mean scores in this study.

Profession Related Groups and the Perceived Tolerance for ECPs Differences Professional Experience Differences

Table 4: *Tolerance for ECPs and professional experience*

Tolerance for ECPs	Till 10	Above 10	MW-U	Sig.
Category 01, Use of unauthorized information				
Offering monetary incentives to sources for confidential information	111.84	138.52	6141.00	.001
Unauthorized use of confidential commercial or government documents	120.11	130.64	7150.00	.20
Claiming oneself to be someone else (false identification)	123.43	127.48	7555.00	.61
Pressuring sources to get news	125.78	125.23	7774.00	.95
Category 02, Journalistic deception				
Unauthorized use of personal documents such as letters and photos	124.98	126.00	7744.00	.89
Getting employed in a firm to get inside information	120.70	130.07	7223.00	.25
Use of hidden cameras or microphones	123.78	127.14	7598.00	.66
Recreating a news event	125.80	125.21	7774.50	.94
Category 03, Information manipulation				
Publishing or airing unverified information	119.59	131.13	7087.00	.03
Receiving money from sources	125.31	125.68	7784.50	.94
Altering or manufacturing quotes	113.72	136.73	6371.00	.02
Altering photos	117.05	133.55	6777.50	.01

(N = 250) Scale ranges from 1 = unacceptable in any situation; 2 = acceptable in certain situations; 3 = acceptable in most situations.

It was observed that under the first conceptual category that is “Use of unauthorized information” the mean scores of the first, third, and fourth items were higher of those journalists who had professional experience above 10 years than those who were professionally experienced just up to 10 years. Whereas, the mean score of the fourth item was a bit bigger of those journalists who had professional experience up to 10 years in comparison with those who had professional experience above 10 years. Similarly, under the second conceptual category “Journalistic deception” having four items it was seen that all the first three items had higher scores of those journalists who were professionally experienced for above 10 years than those who possessed professional experience just till 10 years. Whereas, the mean score of the fourth item under this conceptual category was found bigger of those journalists who had professional experience till 10 years than those whose professional experience was above 10 years. Lastly regarding the third conceptual category said as “Information manipulation” it was found that the mean scores of all the four items were greater for those journalists whose professional experience was above 10 years than those who had a professional experience of just up to 10 years. However, the p values of all the twelve items were statistically non-significant, > 0.05, except the following 4 items that are number one, nine, eleven, and twelve whose Mann-Whitney U-values were statically significant U=6141.00 (Z= -5.16), p=.001; U=7087.00 (Z= -5.16), p=.03; U=6371.00 (Z= -5.16), p=.02; and U=6777.50 (Z= -5.16), p=.01 respectively.

Media Type Differences

Table 5: Tolerance for ECPs and media type

Tolerance for ECPs	Electronic	Print	MW-U	Sig.
Category 01, Use of unauthorized information				
Offering monetary incentives to sources for confidential information	79.04	96.87	2677.00	.02
Unauthorized use of confidential commercial or government documents	79.63	96.65	2706.50	.03
Claiming oneself to be someone else (false identification)	92.60	91.77	3295.00	.91
Pressuring sources to get news	88.92	93.16	3171.00	.58
Category 02, Journalistic deception				
Unauthorized use of personal documents such as letters and photos	86.55	94.05	3052.50	.34
Getting employed in a firm to get inside information	91.79	92.08	3314.50	.97
Use of hidden cameras or microphones	89.96	92.77	3223.00	.71
Recreating a news event	86.38	94.11	3044.00	.33
Category 03, Information manipulation				
Publishing or airing unverified information	90.12	92.71	3231.00	.60
Receiving money from sources	88.66	93.26	3158.00	.35
Altering or manufacturing quotes	85.56	94.42	3003.00	.23
Altering photos	90.62	92.52	3256.00	.78

(N = 250) Scale ranges from 1 = unacceptable in any situation; 2 = acceptable in certain situations; 3 = acceptable in most situations.

In table 5 it was seen that under the first conceptual category “Use of unauthorized information” the mean scores of the first, second, and fourth items were higher of those journalists who worked for print media than those who worked for electronic media. Whereas, the mean score of the third item was found a bit greater of those who worked for electronic media than those who worked for print media. Moreover, under the second conceptual category “Journalistic deception” all four items had higher scores of those journalists who were employed in print media than those who worked in electronic media. Similarly, regarding the third conceptual category “Information manipulation” the mean scores of all the four items were bigger of those journalists who were affiliated with print media than those who had an affiliation with electronic media. However, the p values of all the twelve items were statistically non-significant, > 0.05, except the items number 1 and 11 whose Mann-Whitney U - values were found statically significant U=2677.00 (Z= -5.16), p=.02, and U=2706.50 (Z= -5.16), p=.03 respectively.

Media Organization Language Differences

Table 6: Tolerance for ECPs and media organization language

Tolerance for ECPs	Sindhi	Urdu	MW-U	Sig.
Category 01, Use of unauthorized information				

Offering monetary incentives to sources for confidential information	104.39	110.26	4190.00	.48
Unauthorized use of confidential commercial or government documents	107.87	101.07	4151.00	.42
Claiming oneself to be someone else (false identification)	103.44	112.76	4045.00	.25
Pressuring sources to get news	104.27	110.57	4172.00	.44
Category 02, Journalistic deception				
Unauthorized use of personal documents such as letters and photos	105.68	106.85	4387.50	.89
Getting employed in a firm to get inside information	101.25	118.54	3709.50	.04
Use of hidden cameras or microphones	103.20	113.39	4008.50	.19
Recreating a news event	105.86	106.38	4415.00	.95
Category 03, Information manipulation				
Publishing or airing unverified information	106.82	103.83	4311.00	.58
Receiving money from sources	106.35	105.07	4383.00	.80
Altering or manufacturing quotes	108.45	99.54	4062.50	.25
Altering photos	106.69	104.19	4332.00	.73

(N = 250) Scale ranges from 1 = unacceptable in any situation; 2 = acceptable in certain situations; 3 = acceptable in most situations.

According to table 6, it was seen that under the first conceptual category “Use of unauthorized information” the mean scores of the first, third, and fourth item were bigger of those journalists who worked for Urdu language media than those who worked for Sindhi language media; whereas, the mean score of the second item was comparatively bigger of those journalists who worked for Sindhi language media than those who worked for Urdu language media. Moreover, under the second conceptual category which had also four items and was named “Journalistic deception”, it was found that all the four items rated greater scores of those journalists who were affiliated with Urdu language media than those whose affiliation was with Sindhi language media. Lastly, regarding the third conceptual category “Information manipulation” the mean scores of all the four items stood higher of those journalists whose affiliation was with Sindhi language media than those who were affiliated with Urdu language media. However, p values, of all the twelve items were statistically non-significant, > 0.05, except item number 6 whose Mann-Whitney U-value was statically significant U=3709 (Z= -5.16), p=.04.

Demographic Groups and the Perceived Tolerance for ECP Differences

Educational Differences

Table7: *Tolerance for ECPs and education*

Tolerance for ECPs	Till bachelo r	Above bachelo r	MW-U	Sig.
Category 01, Use of unauthorized information				
Offering monetary incentives to sources for confidential information	126.65	122.81	6360.50	.66

Unauthorized use of confidential commercial or government documents	125.16	126.29	6503.00	.90
Claiming oneself to be someone else (false identification)	129.68	115.74	5830.50	.10
Pressuring sources to get news	130.14	114.67	5750.50	.07
Category 02, Journalistic deception				
Unauthorized use of personal documents such as letters and photos	128.19	119.21	6091	.30
Getting employed in a firm to get inside information	131.64	111.17	5487.50	.02
Use of hidden cameras or microphones	126.58	122.97	6373.00	.67
Recreating a news event	122.09	133.47	5965.00	.20
Category 03, Information manipulation				
Publishing or airing unverified information	125.32	125.91	6531.50	.92
Receiving money from sources	126.09	124.13	6460.00	.73
Altering or manufacturing quotes	123.34	130.54	6184.50	.38
Altering photos	123.98	129.65	6296.50	.49

(N = 250) Scale ranges from 1 = unacceptable in any situation; 2 = acceptable in certain situations; 3 = acceptable in most situations.

In table 7 it was observed that under the first conceptual category “Use of unauthorized information” the mean scores of the first, third, and fourth items were higher of those journalists who were educated up to bachelor than those who were educated above than bachelor. Whereas, the mean score of the second item was a bit greater of those journalists whose education was higher than bachelor in comparison with those who were educated till bachelor. Moreover, under the second conceptual category “Journalistic deception” which had four items it was seen that all the first three items had rated higher scores of those journalists whose education was till bachelor than those whose education was above bachelor. Whereas, the mean score of the fourth item under this conceptual category was higher of those journalists who had education above than bachelor than those whose education was up to bachelor. Lastly, regarding the third conceptual category “Information manipulation” the mean scores of the item first, third, and fourth were higher of those journalists whose education was above bachelor than those who had education till bachelor. On the contrary about the second item the mean score of those journalists who had education till bachelor was higher than those who had education above bachelor. However, the p values of all the twelve items were statistically non-significant, > 0.05, except the item number 6 whose Mann-Whitney U-value was statically significant U=5487.50 (Z=-5.16), p=.02.

Age Category Differences

Table 8: Tolerance for ECPs and age

Tolerance for ECPs	Till 30 year	Above 30 year	MW-U	Sig.
Category 01, Use of unauthorized information				

Offering monetary incentives to sources for confidential information	113.45	130.76	5696.00	.05
Unauthorized use of confidential commercial or government documents	134.13	121.73	5956.50	.17
Claiming oneself to be someone else (false identification)	120.59	127.65	6238.50	.41
Pressuring sources to get news	126.13	125.23	6564.50	.92
Category 02, Journalistic deception				
Unauthorized use of personal documents such as letters and photos	124.02	126.15	6499.50	.81
Getting employed in a firm to get inside information	121.63	127.19	6318.00	.53
Use of hidden cameras or microphones	129.88	123.59	6279.00	.45
Recreating a news event	118.00	128.78	6042.00	.23
Category 03, Information manipulation				
Publishing or airing unverified information	124.31	126.02	6521.50	.77
Receiving money from sources	123.96	126.17	6495.00	.69
Altering or manufacturing quotes	113.38	130.79	5691.00	.03
Altering photos	121.14	127.41	6280.50	.39

(N = 250) Scale ranges from 1 = unacceptable in any situation; 2 = acceptable in certain situations; 3 = acceptable in most situations.

It was seen that under the first conceptual category “Use of unauthorized information” the mean scores of the first and third items were higher for those journalists who were above 30-year-old than those who were just up to 30-year-old. Whereas, the mean scores of second and fourth items, on the contrary, were greater of those journalists whose age was till 30 years in comparison with those whose age was above 30 years. Additionally, under the second conceptual category “Journalistic deception” out of four the item first, second, and fourth had rated higher mean scores of those journalists whose age was above 30 years than those whose age was till 30 years. However, the mean score of the third item under this conceptual category was higher of those journalists whose age was till 30 years than those whose age was above 30 years. Finally, regarding the third conceptual category “Information manipulation” the mean scores of all the four items were higher for those journalists whose age was above 30 years than those who were just up to 30 years old. However, the p values, of all the twelve items were statistically non-significant, > 0.05, except the items number 1 and 11 whose Mann-Whitney U-values were statically significant U=5696.00 (Z= -5.16), p=.05, and U=5691.00 (Z= -5.16), p=.03 respectively.

Monthly Income Differences

Table 9: Tolerance for ECPs and monthly income

Tolerance for ECPs	Till 20000	Above 20000	MW-U	Sig.
	PK Rupees	PK Rupees		
Category 01, Use of unauthorized information				

Offering monetary incentives to sources for confidential information	68.60	74.16	1674.50	.41
Unauthorized use of confidential commercial or government documents	72.31	63.14	1580.00	.19
Claiming oneself to be someone else (false identification)	70.50	68.51	1768.00	.77
Pressuring sources to get news	70.69	67.94	1748.00	.68
Category 02, Journalistic deception				
Unauthorized use of personal documents such as letters and photos	70.19	69.44	1800.50	.91
Getting employed in a firm to get inside information	72.17	63.54	1594.00	.21
Use of hidden cameras or microphones	72.54	62.46	1556.00	.13
Recreating a news event	70.13	69.63	1807.00	.94
Category 03, Information manipulation				
Publishing or airing unverified information	69.82	70.54	1801.00	.86
Receiving money from sources	70.41	68.79	1777.50	.69
Altering or manufacturing quotes	68.25	75.20	1638.00	.28
Altering photos	70.28	69.16	1790.50	.83

(N = 139) Scale ranges from 1 = unacceptable in any situation; 2 = acceptable in certain situations; 3 = acceptable in most situations. (Source: Primary Data)

See table 9 that shows that under the first conceptual category "Use of unauthorized information" the mean scores of second, third, and fourth items were greater for those journalists who earned monthly till 20000/=PKR than those who earned monthly above 20000/=PKR. Whereas, the mean score of the first item on the contrary was greater of those journalists whose monthly income was above 20000/=PKR in comparison with those journalists who earned monthly till 20000/=PKR. Moreover, under the second conceptual category "Journalistic deception" all four items rated bigger scores of those journalists whose monthly income was up to 20000/=PKR than those who earned monthly above 20000/=PKR. Finally, regarding the third conceptual category, "Information manipulation" the mean scores of the first and third item were higher of those journalists whose monthly earning was above 20000/=PKR than those who had monthly income till 20000/=PKR. On the contrary about the second and fourth item, the mean score of those journalists who had monthly income till 20000/=PKR were higher than those whose monthly earning was above 20000/=PKR. However, the p values of all the twelve items were statistically non-significant, > 0.05.

Discussion

This research is mainly motivated by the significance of how journalism ethics are constructed and reconstructed by working journalists in Sindh province, Pakistan. It is assumed that the technological revolution of transformation at the macro level would produce the needs and offer some opportunities for

professional news workers to renegotiate their ethical norms. In this procedure, news workers might accept the idea that ethical situations, values, and norms may vary according to the situations. Those ethical values and norms are also subject to discussion and debate.

In this way, this study analyzed the 'ethical orientation of journalists' by asking their opinion about twelve concrete practices. The data showed that all the four items belonging to the conceptual category of "use of unauthorized information" were unacceptable to the majority of the journalists in any case. However, two items from the second conceptual category "journalistic deception" were acceptable for respondents in certain situations. Those two items are "use of hidden cameras or microphones" and "recreating a news event". These findings indicate the fact that there is a positive rise in investigative journalism among the journalists of this region. As far as the item "use of hidden cameras and microphones" is related, many journalists were of the view that in some critical situations they are bound to do it in order to save themselves in case a source deviates from his statement or sometimes for the greater public good. The data further shows a hopeful indication that all the items of the first conceptual category "use of unauthorized information" is unacceptable to the significant majority of the journalists in this study. Thus, this fact indicates the rising journalistic professionalism in Sindh. The good news is that almost all the items of ethically controversial practices were unacceptable to the considerable majority of the surveyed journalists which shows that slowly and gradually the profession of journalism is taken somewhat seriously.

Interestingly, the data also mentioned that all the four items under the third conceptual category "information manipulation" were supported more by those journalists who worked for print media. Hence, it indicates that journalists associated with print media are more tolerant to the practice of information manipulation as compared to their colleagues who worked for electronic media. Therefore, it can be deduced that print media has a long history in Pakistan as compared to electronic media which was liberalized at the behest of the twentieth century. As result, the foundation of print media in the journalistic profession is much stronger than electronic media. In line with Lo et al.'s (2005) study, the findings of this research indicate the fact that journalistic ethics in Sindh are far from being consensual and unified; added to that professional ethics are subject to various interpretations, negotiation, and understanding.

Conclusion

The central objective of this study was to investigate journalists' ethical orientation regarding "ethically controversial practices" by surveying the journalists in Sindh, Pakistan. Thus, in the survey journalists were asked questions on tolerance toward ethically controversial practices. After analysis of the data, it was concluded that journalists who worked in Sindh were tolerant toward

ethically controversial practices. The factor “use of unauthorized information” was consisted of four items: (1) offering monetary incentives to sources for confidential information; (2) unauthorized use of confidential commercial or government documents; (3) “false identification” and; (4) pressurizing sources to get news”. In this way, the findings showed that majority of the journalists showed considerable tolerance in accepting four items of “use of unauthorized information” and those items were unacceptable for them under any situation. Added to that using hidden microphones or cameras and recreating a news event were acceptable to the surveyed journalists in certain situations mainly because ‘in case of a source deviates from his or her statement in the future. Finally, all the four items of category “information manipulation” were unacceptable under any circumstances for journalists. Moreover, those who worked for print media showed more resistance to ethically controversial practices as compared to their colleagues in electronic media. Thus, it was concluded that according to the findings the journalists in Sindh province, Pakistan was more resistant to ethically controversial practices.

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